

Association of oral ulcers and psychological stress among dental professionals in Konkan region of Maharashtra- A cross sectional study

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Background – Oral ulcers are painful lesions that can arise from various conditions in the oral cavity. The aim of this study was to determine the overall prevalence of oral ulcers and to evaluate their relationship with psychological stress among dental students and professionals.

Methodology – A cross-sectional study was conducted among 560 dental students and professionals, aged 18-50 years. Self-reported questionnaires, including general stress-related questions, were used to assess stress levels. The collected data were analyzed statistically to explore potential correlations between oral ulcers and psychological stress.

Result – Out of the 560 participants, 478 (85.3%) reported having oral ulcers. The prevalence was notably high among dental students, with 75.4% indicating high levels of stress. Statistical analysis showed a significant association between the presence of oral ulcers and elevated psychological stress.

Conclusion – The prevalence of oral ulcers among dental students and professionals in the Konkan region was found to be 85.3%, with a strong association between oral ulcers and psychological stress. These findings underline the need for measures to reduce stress in dental education and professional environments to mitigate the impact of stress on oral health.

Keywords: *Oral Ulcers, Prevalence, Stress.*

Introduction:

Oral ulcers are typically painful lesions that arise from various conditions affecting the oral cavity [1]. They are usually round or oval in shape, with distinct margins, surrounded by a reddish halo, and covered by a yellow or greyish base [2]. These ulcers may appear as primary lesions—developing without any prior lesion, as seen in canker sores—or as secondary lesions, which occur due to trauma, ruptured blisters, or vesicles [3]. Based on their duration and progression, oral ulcers are categorized into two types: acute ulcers, which develop suddenly and resolve in a short period, and chronic ulcers, which appear gradually and persist for longer durations [4,5].

Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis (RAS) represents a common type of oral ulcer. These ulcers are benign yet painful, shallow, and round, bordered by an erythematous halo and covered by a yellowish-gray fibrinous layer. The term “aphthous” is derived from the Greek word “aphtha”, meaning ulcer [6]. Globally, the prevalence of oral ulcers is about 4%, with aphthous ulcers being the most frequent, affecting nearly 25% of individuals who experience oral ulceration. RAS generally occurs in non-keratinized regions such as the lips, buccal mucosa, ventral surface of the tongue, floor of the mouth, and soft palate [7]. Chronic forms of oral ulcers are often linked to systemic or autoimmune conditions like oral lichen planus, pemphigus vulgaris, mucous membrane pemphigoid, lupus erythematosus, mycoses, and certain bacterial or parasitic infections [8]. Psychological factors, especially acute stress and anxiety, have been strongly associated with the onset and worsening of RAS. Severe stress can influence immune regulation by increasing leukocyte activity at sites of inflammation [9]. Symptoms such as pain during speaking, chewing, and swallowing, along with general discomfort, may restrict food and fluid intake, and can negatively influence interpersonal interactions and self-esteem [10]. Hence, clinical evaluation, mental health status, dental requirements, and patients’ personal perceptions must all be considered in management.

Methodology:

Study design:

This cross-sectional study was carried among 560 dental students and dental professionals of Yogita Dental College and Hospital of Konkan region. Study enrolled subjects from age group 18-50 years. The ethical clearance for the current study was obtained from Institutional Ethical Committee. Informed consent was obtained from the willing participants. The data was collected using Convenience sampling technique. The subjects who did not consent to participate in the study were excluded.

Data collection:

The participants were briefed about the purpose of the study. The data was collected using self-reported questionnaires, circulated through Google forms by investigator. The questionnaire had four sections.

Questionnaire:

The first section included demographic details comprising of age, gender and year of study, second section records oral ulcer prevalence and characteristics, third section includes questions regarding stress assessment and psychological factors and the last section involves questions related to stress-oral ulcer relationship.

Ethical considerations:

Institutional ethics approval was obtained.

Statistical analysis:

Table 1: Socio-demographic and clinical profile of the dental professionals.

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18-22 yrs	418	74.6
	23-27 yrs	112	20.0
	28-35 yrs	18	3.2
	36-50 yrs	12	2.1
Gender	Female	456	81.4
	Male	102	18.2
	Prefer not to say	2	.4
Academic status	INTERN	44	7.9
	PG	22	3.9
	STAFF	22	3.9
	UG	472	84.3

Table 2: Duration, severity and factors affecting oral ulcers

Sr.no	Questions	Response
1.	Frequency of oral ulcers in past 12 months	Frequently [64(11.4%)], occasionally [122(21.8%)], Rarely [292(52.1%)], Never [82(14.6%)]
2.	Duration of Oral Ulcer	1-3 days [354(63.2%)], 4-7 days [184(32.9%)],8-14 days [12(2.1%)]
3.	Is the ulcer painful	Mild [282(50.4%)], Moderate [224(40%)], Severe [16(2.9%)], No pain [38(6.8%)]
4.	Area of occurrence	Tongue [152(27.1%)], Cheeks [244(43.6%)], Lips[120(21.6%)], Gingiva[44(7.9%)]
5.	Type of food prefer	Veg [282(50.4%)], Non-Veg [194(34.6%)], Spicy [74(13.2%)], Salty [2(4%)], Acidic [8(1.4%)]
6.	Primary source of stress	Academic (Workload/ Examination) [422(75.4%)], Clinical Performance/Patient care [74(13.2%)], Financial concerns [28(5%)], Personal relationships/family issues [36(6.4%)]
7.	Factors affecting stress	Lack of sleep [176(31.4%)], Poor nutrition/Skipping meals [176(31.4%)], Physical trauma (Biting, dental procedure) [154(27.5%)],Harmonal Changes[54(9.6%)]

Results:

The present study carried out among 560 dental students and dental professionals in past 12 months 11.4% experienced oral ulcer more frequently,21.8% experienced occasionally, 52.1% experienced oral ulcer rarely and whereas 14.6% had never experienced ulcer. Of them 63.2% had ulcers lasting for 1-3 days,32.9% for 4-7 days and 2.1% for 8-14 days With respect to the 560 contributors, a majority had lack of sleep 31.4% and poor nutrition 31.4%, followed by physical trauma 27.5% and hormonal changes 9.6%.The majority of patient around 50.4% experiencing mild pain, followed by moderate pain around 40% , patient experiencing severe pain with 2.9% and around 6.8% not experiencing pain. The predominant area of occurrence is cheeks 43.6%, followed by tongue 27.1%, Lips 25.6% and least followed by gingiva by 7.9%.

Discussion:

Ulceration of the oral mucosa is one of the painful oral lesions that make patients to seek dental treatment. It usually accompanied by pain during speaking and mastication [11]. Oral ulcers are encountered frequently in our daily practice; it causes a lot of suffering and agony for the patients throughout their life. Clinically; oral ulcers are usually painful, shallow, round in shape with an erythematous halo covered by a yellowish-gray fibro membranous layer [12]. Recurrent aphthous ulcers (RAU) considered the most type of ulcerations affecting oral mucosa. It has an estimated point prevalence of 4% in the United States [13]. The present study was designed to determine the prevalence of oral ulcers among selected sample of Konkan population of Maharashtra and to determine factors associated with the development of these lesions. The result of the present study showed that the prevalence of oral ulcers among the study sample was 85.3%. This prevalence rate is higher than that reported in other studies that performed among other countries such as Yemen 43.5%, United states 40%, Japan 31%, Iraq 28.2%, Iran 25.2%, Turkey 25.5%, and Saudi Arabia 14% In the present study, the sites of occurrence of oral ulcers as reported were tongue, lips, cheeks and gingiva. The results of our study were different with that of other study conducted among population of Yemen which revealed that gingiva was the most common site of oral ulcer. whereas in our study buccal mucosa and tongue was the most common site of appearance [14]. As mentioned before, oral ulcers can be caused by a variety of factors, one of

the most common associated risk factors of developing recurrent aphthous ulcers is stress and psychological problems. Studies among US dental students and western population of Maharashtra, India was reported this association [15]. The present study failed to find a significant association between stress and recurrent aphthous stomatitis and this also can be owned to the age, socioeconomic status of the most patient in the present study sample and their marital status and occupation which usually exposed to less stress compared to older and married people and other stressful careers. As they undergo different physiological and hormonal change throughout their life, in our case female patients were found to be more exposed to oral ulcerative lesions compared to male counterparts (81.4% and 18.2%) this findings has been agreed by study among Yemen female patients (53.9% and 46.1%), Jordanians female patients (53% and 45%) respectively [16]. In addition to this Patil et al. also reported that females (56.3%) were more habitually affected compared to males (43.7%) and the results were statistically significant. It could be due to more level of stress among females due to emotional conditions which can have an effect on their immune response. Also, hormonal changes during pregnancy and menstruation also have an impact on stress [17]. Oral lesions caused by ROUs may be very painful and make it difficult to talk, eat, or drink. It is hypothesized that stress might set in motion the processes responsible for the onset of ROUs, resulting in pain that can have deleterious effects on the person and elicit even more stress. Unfortunately, this may cause a vicious cycle in which stress causes ulcers, which in turn causes more stress [18]. Researching the frequency of ROUs is crucial because it reveals both the prevalence of the problem and the variables that may be contributing to it among students. The percentage of dental professionals who have ROUs and require dental care may be estimated by learning more about the disease's incidence and geographic distribution in konkan population of Maharashtra. Oral doctors may benefit from knowing the higher prevalence of recurrent oral ulcers to make a correct diagnosis. It will also help in providing different treatment information to the patient that might improve their condition. In our study, comparatively 75.4% of patients experienced mouth ulcers, accordingly 46.2% of students were stressed out by the research conducted by George et al in 2016 and Verma S et al in 2023 experienced 32.7% of the patients experienced ulcers when survey was done at examination time.

Conclusion:

This study found a high prevalence of oral ulcers (85.3%) among dental students and professionals in the Konkan region, with stress being a contributing factor. While no strong causal link was established, the data suggests a moderate association between stress and the occurrence of oral ulcers, particularly among females (81.4%). The most common sites of ulceration were the cheeks and tongue. The findings emphasize the need for stress management programs in dental institutions to reduce the psychological burden and improve oral health. Effective stress-reduction strategies could help mitigate the impact of oral ulcers on students and professionals.

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